

(0.337) at harvest, followed by P in leaf at 60 d and in stem at harvest. The indirect effects of P in stem, grain, leaf, and sterile panicles via root were all

positive. An indirect positive effect was found via stem at harvest. The direct and indirect contributions of leaf and sound grain were negative. ■

Manoharsali as checks were field tested at research stations and in field trials in Gerua, Tinsukia, and Suklivoria for 1-6 yr. Trials were laid out at 20- × 15-cm spacing with 2-3 seedlings/hill. Forty kg N as urea was applied in three splits before planting, at tillering, and at panicle initiation; 20 kg/ha each of P and K were applied in the form of single superphosphate and muriate of potash as basal.

IET6666 showed wide adaptability and stability in grain yield under the agroecological conditions of Assam (Table 2). It flowered in 115-120 d and matured in 145-157 d.

The variety is being evaluated for release as Lakhimi for Assam wet season. ■

Integrated germplasm improvement

IET6666, a new high-yielding rice variety for Assam

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IET6666, a long-duration, high-yielding variety evolved from RP31-49-2/Patnai

23 by the Directorate of Rice Research in Hyderabad, is suitable for low-lying fields and cloudy weather conditions during wet season. Its coarse grain and intermediate plant height are preferred by the majority of farmers in Assam.

Agronomic characteristics are given in Table 1.

IET6666, 12 other promising cultivars with similar duration, and Mahsuri and

Table 1. Morphological and physiological characteristics of IET6666 and check variety Manoharsali at Titabar, Assam, India.

Character	IET6666	Manoharsali
Plant height (cm)	118.73	148.53
Duration	145	148
Panicles (no./m ²)	257	242
Filled grains (no./panicle)	103	83
1000-grain weight (g)	23.22	24.55
Total dry matter at flowering (kg/ha)	116.76	146.56
Leaf area index	4.58	5.80
Total chlorophyll content at flowering (mg/g fresh wt)	2.23	3.43
N content in leaf tissues at flowering (%)	2.18	1.23
Solar energy utilization efficiency for dry matter (%)	1.87	0.81
Solar energy utilization for grain yield (%)	0.55	0.25

Table 2. Yields of IET6666 and check varieties at different locations in Assam, India 1978-88.

Year	Location	Yield (t/ha)		
		IET6666	Mahsuri	Manoharsali
1978	Titabar	3.4	2.7	-
	Karimganj	3.0	3.3	-
1979	Titabar	5.2	3.8	-
	Karimganj	2.9	3.9	-
1980	Titabar	5.0	4.5	-
	Karimganj	3.6	3.5	-
1982	Titabar	3.8	-	3.0
	Karimganj	4.4	-	1.9
1983	Titabar	3.9	-	2.0
	Karimganj	4.4	-	3.5
1984	Titabar	5.3	-	3.1
1985	Titabar	5.3	-	3.2
1986	Titabar	5.2	-	3.2
1987	Titabar	5.4	-	3.2
1988	Titabar	5.1	-	2.6
1984 on-farm trials	Gerua	6.4	-	5.2
	Tinsukia	5.1	-	4.2
	Suklivoria	3.9	-	4.0

Performance of IR46 and IR10781-143-2-3 under transplanted rainfed lowland conditions in Nepal

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In Nepal, 88% of the rice area (1.45 million ha in 1988) is in the subtropical climatic region of the Tarai belt (67-250 m altitude), the Inner Tarai region, and equivalent climatic region of river basin areas and valleys up to 900 m altitude.

Table 1. Yields of IR46 and IR10781-143-2-3 at 4 sites in subtropical Nepal, 1983-86.

Variety	Yield (t/ha)					Increase over check(%)	Experiment site ^a and time
	Tarahara	Parwanipur	Rampur	Nepalganj	Mean		
IR46	4.6	2.6	3.0	3.2	3.4	142	Research stations, 1983-84
Improved check Bindeshori	2.4	2.2	2.0	2.8	2.4	100	
IR46	4.8	2.6	2.4	4.2 ^a	3.5	114	Farmers' fields, 1985-86
Improved check Masuli	3.3	2.0	-	3.9	3.1	100	
IR10781	3918	2956	2692	2981	3.1	105	Research stations, 1984-85
Improved check Bindeshori	3562	3001	2512	2897	3.0	100	
IR10781	4840	2818	3750	4150	3.9	127	Farmers' fields, 1985-86
Improved check Masuli	3292	2012	-	3900	3.1	100	

^a Farmer's field result of this location is from Nawal Parasi area. Each location includes the results from various farmers' fields.